

Germany

This report describes the structure of the national higher education system in Germany, focusing on the institutional types as defined by national categories. It builds on the Eurydice Report on the national higher education system but complements it with quantitative information on the role of higher education institution (HEI) types in national systems, based on data derived from the European Tertiary Education Register (<http://www.eter-project.eu>) for the period 2011-2020.

Types of Higher Education Institutions

According to Eurydice¹, the German higher education system comprises three types of higher education institutions (HEIs):

- Universities (*Universitäten*) and equivalent institutions of higher education that only offer individual courses of study, such as theological universities² (*Theologische Hochschulen*), or that focus on specific areas, such as Universities of education³ (*Pädagogische Hochschulen*) in the field of educational science (only in Baden-Württemberg).
- Universities of Art, Film and Music⁴ (*Kunsthochschulen*) that offer courses of studies in the visual, design and performing arts as well as in the area of film, television and media, and in various music subjects.
- Universities of applied sciences (*Fachhochschulen*) characterised by an application-oriented teaching and research, a usually integrated semester of practical training, as well as professors, who have, in addition to their academic qualifications, gained professional experience outside the field of higher education. In some Länder *Fachhochschulen* are called *Hochschulen für angewandte Wissenschaften* (higher education institutions of applied sciences). A special role is played by the Universities of applied sciences of Public Administration (*Verwaltungsfachhochschulen*), which train civil servants for careers in the so-called higher level of the civil service.

In addition, Germany's tertiary sector also includes either state-run or state-recognised professional academies (*Berufsakademien*), as well as professional colleges (*Fachschulen*) offering continuing vocational education and training for skills upgrading. These are not covered by ETER.

¹ <https://eurydice.eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-education-systems/germany/types-higher-education-institutions>

² Since 2023 Eurydice uses the translation “theological colleges” for this type

³ Since 2023 Eurydice uses the translation “Pädagogische Hochschulen in the field of educational science” for this type

⁴ Since 2023 Eurydice uses the translation “Colleges of art and music” for this type

Main institutional characteristics. Legal status and the right to award a PhD

Table 1 below provides a quantitative overview of the main institutional characteristics by HEI type. Universities (*Universitäten*) are mostly public institutions and, with very few exceptions, have the right to award PhDs. In total, about 30% of all German HEIs are Universities and equivalent institutions. Universities of applied sciences (*Fachhochschulen*) and University of Applied Sciences of Public Administration (*Verwaltungsfachhochschulen*) account combined for almost 60% of all German HEIs, however, only a small fraction of them awards PhDs. Universities of Art (*Kunsthochschulen*) account for the remaining 12% of all HEIs and are mostly PhD awarding. Almost one third of all HEIs, mostly *Fachhochschulen*, in Germany are private.

Table 1. Institutional type and legal status by HEI type, 2020

Category		N	Public	Private	PhD awarding
University	Universität	107	85	22	96
University of Applied Sciences	Fachhochschulen	199	105	94	16
University of Applied Sciences of Public Administration	Verwaltungsfachhochschulen	29	28	1	0
University of Arts	Kunsthochschulen	48	45	3	31
University of Education	Pädagogische Hochschulen	6	6	0	6
University of Theology	Theologische Hochschulen	10	0	10	9
Total		399	269	130	158

Note: Numbers reflect inclusion in ETER

Institutional history. Older and younger institutional types

Data on the HEI foundation year provide information on the history of Germany's higher education and its evolution over time. Figure 1 overleaf shows that, despite ancient historical roots, the expansion of the system in terms of HEI population is relatively recent. While the University of Heidelberg, the oldest German university, dates back to 1386, 31 HEIs were founded before the 20th century, including one University of Theology (Paderborn) and five Universities of Arts. Overall, however, German HEIs are much younger; only one-quarter of the HEIs were founded before WWII. The figure shows two distinct patterns of expansion. First, the number (and size) of universities has been increased – half of the German universities were founded after 1963. The second wave of expansion was initiated with the formal creation of Universities of applied sciences (*Fachhochschulen*) in 1968: while few of them pre-existed that decision, their formal recognition as a HEI type

started a new expansion process, which continues until today – half of the *Fachhochschulen* were founded after 1992. Among the 34 HEIs in ETER founded after 2009, 24 are *Fachhochschulen* and only seven universities.

Figure 1. Foundation year of HEIs by type

Students

In contrast to the number of institutions, in terms of the number of students enrolled, Universities still account for nearly two-thirds of all students and Universities of applied sciences (*Fachhochschulen*) for one-third. The other institutional types play a relatively minor role in the aggregate (see Figure 2). While almost one out of three German HEIs in ETER is private, these enrol only 11% of the students and, therefore, play a limited role in the national higher education system.

According to different institutional mandates, we also observe systematic differences between educational levels: Universities of applied sciences (*Fachhochschulen*) account for half of the bachelor students and one-third of the master students, while doctorates and long master's degrees enrolments (without an intermediate bachelor's degree) are the remit of universities.

This pattern closely matches the policy intention to focus *Fachhochschulen* on shorter professional curricula; however, their role has become important also in master education.

Figure 2. Students by level and type of HEI, 2020

Note: Total students include ISCED 6-7

Personnel

People are a core resource for HEIs, as their competences are essential for teaching, undertaking research and producing scientific output. In that respect, ETER provides a rich set of data moving beyond the information available in EUROSTAT, which allows to analyze the composition of personnel by type of HEI and characteristics such as gender, nationality, educational field and, from 2020 onwards, levels of seniority.

As shown by Figure 3, there are major differences between HEIs in size, as measured by total personnel in full time equivalents (FTE), and in the personnel composition. With an average of nearly 4,000 FTEs, Universities are significantly larger than Universities of applied sciences (400 FTE) and employ almost 80% of all personnel of the German higher education system. As of the personnel composition, academic personnel and research and support and administrative personnel account each for about half of total personnel. Research and teaching assistants (RTAs), PhD and master students supporting research and teaching activities, are missing for Germany.

Figure 3. Personnel (FTE) by category and type of HEI, 2020

Note: Research and teaching assistants missing

Since the data collection 2020, ETER also includes information on academic staff seniority level based on a classification jointly developed by OECD and EUROSTAT⁵. Combined with information on gender, this information allows measuring two critical issues, i.e. career prospects of academic staff and the so-called leaky pipeline, i.e. the fact that the share of female academic staff decreases systematically with seniority levels.

As of Germany, data (see Figure 4) show a steep hierarchy, with 51% of academic personnel at the junior level and only 12% at the senior level. While a reasonable gender balance has been achieved for junior personnel, but only 26% of senior-level academic personnel are female (see Figure 4).

⁵ OECD (2022), Education at a Glance, Paris, pp. 412-413.

Figure 4. Academic personnel by seniority level and gender (HC), 2020

A final important dimension is internationality since it is generally considered as beneficial for the quality of research and education. In ETER, this is measured by the share of academic personnel not having the citizenship of the country ('foreigners'). As shown by Figure 5, the German higher education is characterized by a relative low level of internationality with only 13% of foreign academic personnel in 2020. While in universities over 15% of academic personnel are foreign, this share drops to 6% in universities of applied sciences. Internationality is therefore associated with research orientation of HEIs. A slow increase over the last ten years can also be observed.

Figure 5. Share of foreign academic personnel (HC) by type of HEI, 2011 and 2020

Note: 2020 data are not fully comparable to previous years due to change in definitions

Financial resources

As illustrated in Figure 6, in the year 2020, Universities account for almost three-quarters of financial revenues and academic staff of the whole HEI system, i.e. substantially more than their share of students. This broadly corresponds to the fact that Universities also have an important research function. This difference is also reflected in the composition of revenues (see Figure 7, where Universities earn a large proportion of revenues from (research-related) third-party funds). Overall, state allocation remains dominant for all institutional types in Germany, while student fees play a minor role.

Figure 6. Resources, academic personnel and total students enrolled by type of HEI, 2020

Figure 7. Composition of resources by type of HEI, 2020

Changing roles over time

When observed through the lens of the number of students, data show a pattern of increase with the number of enrolled students increasing by 25% from 2011 to 2020 and with a slight increase of the share of Universities of applied sciences (*Fachhochschulen*) from 33% to 38% of the students enrolled.

This closely matches patterns of institutional expansion, as from 2011 to 2020, 27 new HEIs were founded, 20 of them being *Fachhochschulen*. Overall, the observed pattern over the considered period is of moderate expansion within the observed institutional structure.

Figure 8. Students enrolled by type of HEI, 2011-2020

As shown by Figure 9, with an increase of 26% from 2011 to 2020, the number of academic personnel (FTE) in German HEIs kept pace with the increase in the number of students. Like for students, the increase of academic personnel was stronger in universities of applied sciences (+38%) than in universities (+23%).

Figure 9. Academic personnel (FTE) by type of HEI, 2011-2020

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